

Initial Experimental Validation of a Microwave Imaging System to Monitor Liver Microwave Thermal Ablation

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Abstract—This study presents the initial experimental validation of a mono-static microwave imaging system to monitor liver microwave thermal ablation. The system consists of a tank filled with a coupling medium in which a 3D-printed phantom mimicking the ablation region is embedded. A slot-loaded Vivaldi antenna is moved in front of the phantom along a linear path, measuring the S-parameters on a finite number of positions. Both simulation and measurement results are found to agree each other. The differential signal of the microwave imaging system with and without the presence of the phantom is over -90 dB, which is above the detection capacity of commercial VNA. The experimental validation of the system paves the way for the design of a multi-static microwave imaging system.

Index Terms—microwave imaging system, microwave thermal ablation, experimental validation

I. INTRODUCTION

Liver cancer is a malignancy that occurs in the liver cells. In 2020, it was the sixth most common cancer and the third most deadly cancer worldwide, with an increasing yearly fatality rate [1]. Due to its societal relevance and impact, effective treatments to remove liver cancer have been investigated over the years [1]. Among them, thermal ablation is currently identified as the alternative treatment to conventional surgery, being minimally invasive, low-cost, and thanks to the rapidity of the procedure [2].

Over the years, real-time monitoring of liver thermal ablation has become a big challenge, because the existing modalities like computed tomography (CT scan), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography (PET), and ultra-sonic imaging (US) have limitations in the applications at hand, that makes them unable to provide real-time temperature values [3]. Therefore, the assessment of the ablation procedure heavily relies on the clinician's

experience [4]. In this framework, microwave imaging (MWI) can represent a potential candidate, as it is portable, low cost, capable of real-time imaging, and harmless, due to the adoption of non-ionizing radiations.

MWI uses the field backscattered by the probed region to build a map of the dielectric properties of an unknown target from the knowledge of the scattered electromagnetic field [5]. During microwave liver thermal ablation treatment, the water molecules in the ablation zone dramatically reduce due to the heating. This process yields a change in dielectric properties values in the ablation zone compared to the untreated liver [6]. Microwave imaging can take advantage of such a significant change in the dielectric properties of ablated tissue, compared to the untreated liver [7]. In fact, due to the presence of the ablated zone, the scattered field in the region of interest changes from its value, before the beginning of the ablation. If the sensors in the MWI system detect such a field, an image of the treated region can be formed by solving an inverse scattering problem, which reveals the position and the dielectric map in the domain of interest [7]. According to existing knowledge of the correspondence between the liver's dielectric properties values and temperature [6], it is then possible to derive the local temperature in the ablation zone and hence derive the ablation stage.

In [8], the optimal working conditions of a MWI system to monitor thermal ablation of the liver were assessed. According to that analysis, the 0.5-2 GHz frequency band is the one adopted to operate the device, and a coupling medium with a permittivity value close to 23 through the frequency range is identified as the needed means to favor the penetration of the field into the body. These conditions give a trade-off between penetration depth, imaging resolution, and antenna dimension. Considering these operating conditions, a multi-static MWI system for real-time monitoring of a liver thermal ablation procedure was

Figure 1(a) MWI system configuration (b) Experimental validation of the MWI system

Figure 2 Antenna simulation and measurement S-parameters and differential signals at position 4

designed and numerically assessed in [7]. In particular, results show such a MWI system is not only capable of localizing the target, but it can also identify the ablation zone at different ablation stages.

Following the positive outcomes of this in-silico assessment, the initial experimental validation of the system is presented in the present study. In particular, for the sake of simplicity, instead of implementing an antenna array as in [7], a simpler, mono-static version of the system is considered. The goal is to provide a first demonstration of the possibility of measuring a meaningful signal due to the changes in the dielectric properties in the region of interest in the operating conditions adopted to design the system. To this end, the antenna is immersed into a tank filled with a properly designed coupling medium [8] and moved along a linear path parallel to an elliptical phantom mimicking the ablation zone.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Description of the experimental set-up

The top-view of the configuration adopted for the experiment is shown in Figure 1(a). The set-up consist of an antenna immersed in the coupling liquid and moved in front of an elliptical phantom mimicking the ablated region.

Fig.1(b) shows the actual implementation of the experiment, with the antenna and phantom immersed in the tank.

The MWI antenna is a slot-loaded Vivaldi antenna, designed to have compact dimension and working in the required frequency band. The antenna is 3.5 cm away from the elliptical phantom, and the S-parameters are measured at 7 different positions. The distance between each position is equal to 2cm. The simulations of the MWI system were performed with the CST software (Dassault Systemes, France).

The experimental validation of the system is done by connecting the antenna to the VNA (P5002A Keysight Streamline, 9 kHz to 9 GHz) and placing the antenna in the coupling medium, which has the permittivity value close to 23 along with the 500 MHz to 3 GHz bandwidth. The coupling medium recipe is modified from the one in [9] by adding guar gum powder. The guar gum in this recipe can increases viscosity to the mixture so as to prevent the oil and water from separating. The ablated liver phantom is a 3D-printed elliptical shell made of acrylonitrile butadiene styrene material and filled with Triton-X 100/water mixture, which has the same dielectric properties as the ablated liver.

To simulate the differential imaging conditions assumed in the imaging application, two measurements are done for each position of the antenna, one without the phantom and the other with the phantom filled with a mixture mimicking ablated liver tissue.

III. NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The comparison between simulations and measurement results of the antenna at position 4 is reported in Figure 2. The S-parameter of the antenna with and without the presence of the phantom is given. It is found that a quite good agreement is achieved, especially below 2GHz, which is the frequency band useful for imaging purposes according to [8]. The differential signal of the S-parameters with and without the presence of the phantom is reported in the same figure. In both simulations and measurements, the differential signal level is between 30 and 40 dB below the measured signal level, thus being well within the dynamic range of the commercial VNA. As such, the useful differential signal can be accurately measured by the device.

Finally, the simulated differential signals of the antenna placed at all 7 positions are reported in Figure 3, while the measured differential signals are reported in Figure 4. As it can be seen, both results are in good agreement and allow to appreciate the fact that the useful differential signal level is within the detection capacity of a VNA.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study shows the initial experimental validation of a MWI system to monitor liver thermal ablation, in which a slot-loaded Vivaldi antenna is moved in front of an ablated liver phantom to measure the S-parameters at 7 different positions. The measured S-parameters are in close agreement

with the simulation results. The differential signal level of the S-parameters stays well above the noise floor of the VNA for all positions, thus being reliably measured by the device.

At the conference, a preliminary analysis of the imaging capabilities for these simplified conditions will be presented.

Future work will include the experimental assessment of the MWI system with more antenna elements in the array configuration and the reconstruction imaging of the target.

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Figure 3 Antenna simulated differential signal at all positions

Figure 4 Antenna measured differential signal at all positions